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Naturalised Chinese in the Australasian Colonies: Rights, Race and Mobility

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Keynote Lecture, 23 November 2019

9.00am to 10.15am

Among the Chinese migrants who came to Australasian colonies were several thousand who sought naturalisation as a British subject. In New South Wales, Chinese were able to be naturalised before 1861 and between 1867 and 1888, during which time more than 950 did so. In Victoria, more than 2500 Chinese had been naturalised by 1888. And in New Zealand, around 500 Chinese were naturalised before Chinese naturalisation was prohibited in 1908. Naturalisation had significant implications for Chinese in the colonies – regarding residence, mobility and family formation among other things – and naturalised Chinese, as individuals, appear in many histories, particularly merchants like Quong Tart, Louis Ah Mouy and Choie Sew Hoy. Yet the history of Chinese naturalisation itself has received comparatively little attention.

In this lecture I will consider the connected histories of Chinese naturalisation in the British settler colonies of Australasia – specifically the Tasman colonies of New South Wales, Victoria, Tasmania and New Zealand. I will explore the laws and policies governing Chinese naturalisation and consider how naturalisation was connected to specific anti-Chinese laws, particularly legislation that controlled Chinese mobility across colonial borders. Using the case study of New Zealand, I will further examine the shifting patterns of Chinese naturalisation across the second half of the nineteenth century through analysis of the naturalisation files of 500 naturalised Chinese New Zealanders.

1. TITLE SLIDE

2. CSDS SPECIAL ISSUE

3. TITLE SLIDE

Introduction

- My keynote today draws on ongoing research I am doing as part of a project on the history of Chinese naturalisation in British settler colonies around the Pacific Rim – in New Zealand, in Australia (specifically NSW) and in Canada (specifically British Columbia)
- In this project I'm looking at the legal and administrative history of Chinese naturalisation, and also at the lives of Chinese migrants who became British subjects – who they were, why they became naturalised, and how naturalisation / British subjecthood shaped their experience of life in the settler colonies
- In this history of Chinese naturalisation, we can see connections of law and governance around citizenship, nationality and Chinese restriction, but also of movement and mobility between China, Hong Kong and the colonies, and between the colonies themselves
- As I've progressed with my research, it's these questions of movement and mobility that have particularly interested me – for Chinese migrants, naturalisation might have been about settlement, but it was also about freedom of movement across colonial borders
- Today, I'd also like us to think about three broader things:
 - 1. I want to raise **the question of gender within Chinese Australasian history**
 - The subjects of my research in this project, Chinese who were naturalised, were pretty much all male. So, as a feminist historian, as someone who has often focused on histories of women and the family, how do I bring gender to bear on this history? How do we do it more generally when we know the large majority of Chinese immigrants to colonial Australasia were men? In my case here, in part I can do this by inserting women's stories into the history – mostly as wives and daughters of naturalised Chinese – but it's also by acknowledging the gendered character of Chinese migration and of the British colonial legal framework of which naturalisation was a part.

- 2. I want us to contemplate **a geographic refiguring of Chinese Australian history** – and this comment is directed primarily to the Australians here.
- I think we need to be including New Zealand more explicitly in our thinking about Chinese migration and settlement, especially in the nineteenth century
- And so, in my talk today I'm going to focus on what might be called the Tasman colonies: New Zealand, Tasmania, Victoria and New South Wales
- 3. I want to **emphasise the importance of getting the details of legal and administrative history right** in the histories we tell
- The lives of Chinese in New Zealand and Australia were constrained by legal and bureaucratic systems that white colonists never had to confront, and without really understanding those systems, it's easy for us to make perhaps misguided assumptions about their lives, or perpetuate stories that continue to Other them
- In thinking about nationality and citizenship, if we get the details wrong we can overlook people's agency or the ways they asserted their citizenship rights – for example, by voting in election or by questioning the race-based discrimination they faced, based on their legal rights under British law as British subjects
- So, much of what I'm going to do today is to explore the legal and administrative contexts of Chinese naturalisation, to give you a sense of this as a background to the lives of naturalised Chinese British subjects and their families.

Subjects and aliens

4. FLORENCE BELLAMY AND HARRY BAGNALL

- My ancestors were migrants to the Australian colonies – the earliest arrived in New South Wales from Germany via England in the 1850s, the latest arrived here in New Zealand in the 1910s
- My German ancestor was naturalised as a British subject in New South Wales just before the turn of the 20th century, while the rest, who were of English, Scots and Northern Irish origins, were already British subjects by birth

- Being white and British, they were unproblematically seen as ‘settlers’, and as Britons, my mobile ancestors moved easily both to the colonies and then between them as whim or circumstance dictated
- This handsome couple are my ancestors, my paternal great grandparents, Henry Bagnall and Florence Bellamy, who married in Sydney in 1895
- Henry had come from Dudley in England, while Florence was born in Dunedin
- Her father, John Thomas Bellamy, an Englishman, epitomised, I think, the mobility of Britons within the Empire and within the colonies. Over his life, John Thomas Bellamy, lived in England, goldrush Victoria, goldrush Otago, and then New South Wales. There were no restrictions on his movement or settlement.

5. QUONG TART AND HARRY BAGNALL

- For Chinese migrants, however – men like Sydney merchant Quong Tart, for example, seen here with my great grandfather at a cycle club race in Sydney in about 1898 – their ability to travel to and between the colonies was not always so simple, nor was their ability to make a new home here.
- Legal status as and racial identity as ‘Chinese’, two separate things that were often conflated into one, made them both ‘aliens’ and ‘coloured aliens’
- Until 1949, a person living in Australia or New Zealand was classified as either a ‘British subject’ or an ‘alien’ – that is a ‘non-British subject’ or a ‘foreigner’. It was only in the second half of the twentieth century that the legal concept of ‘New Zealand citizen’ or ‘Australian citizen’ formally came into being.
- Anyone born within the British Empire at this time was a British subject – so Chinese born in Hong Kong and those born in the Australasian colonies were British subjects, something that was at times perplexing to colonial authorities
- The history of natural-born Chinese British subjects is a whole other very interesting part of the story, which I won’t really touch on today
- Naturalisation was the process by which an ‘alien’ could become a British subject, gaining the rights and privileges that came with that. These related to things like residency, purchasing land, the vote, and social welfare. Understanding what these ‘rights and privileges’ were can be challenging, and it was often more about what aliens could not do, rather than what British subjects could do, and there were changes over time and differences between jurisdictions. Questions around land and property ownership can be particularly confusing.

- Quong Tart is perhaps typical of the sort of Chinese migrant we might imagine took naturalisation in the colonies – those who had settled, were socially and politically active, had bought property, ran businesses, and had established homes and families here.
- There are certainly many other naturalised Chinese who fit a similar profile, including, here in New Zealand, merchants and storekeepers like Dunedin’s famed Choie Sew Hoy or Christian missionaries like Timothy Fay Loie

6. TIMOTHY FAY LOIE AND FAMILY

- These were Chinese men for whom naturalisation seems to provide a clear demonstration of their commitment to a future in the colonies, and of their choice to view the colonies as a new ‘home’ (although not always their only one).

Naturalisation and Chinese restriction

- Over the past twenty years, I’ve worked with many Australians in uncovering the stories of their Chinese ancestors, stories that for many were hidden or unknown, particularly in families that intermarried.
- I began to notice that quite a few of these Chinese ancestors, men who had arrived in the nineteenth century, had become naturalised – yet the story we hear most often in historical scholarship is that of the prohibition of Chinese naturalisation, of the substantial periods of time when Chinese could not become British subjects in Australia and New Zealand
- Yet the lives of these naturalised Chinese – and not just the notable ones like Quong Tart or Timothy Fay Loie – suggested to me that naturalisation was an example of how the law could function in both an inclusionary and exclusionary way towards Chinese in the colonies.
- In the nineteenth century, Chinese were being naturalised at the same time as anti-Chinese laws and policies were in place. What exactly then was the relationship between Chinese restriction and naturalisation?
- My study builds on the work of other scholars who have begun to look at naturalisation and citizenship of Chinese in various contexts. There is, of course, Nigel Murphy’s work here in New Zealand, and other work by Peter Prince, Kim Rubenstein, and the late Kevin Wong Hoy in Australia.

- Anti-Chinese laws and policies shaped the histories of Chinese migration and settlement in New Zealand and Australia, with the earliest Chinese restriction laws being enacted in Victoria in the mid-1850s
- These laws differed according to jurisdiction and over time, but they covered areas like immigration, residence, employment, the franchise, social welfare, military service, and citizenship
- New Zealand restricted the naturalisation of Chinese migrants from 1908 to 1951, after the government came to believe that Chinese only sought naturalisation to evade restrictive immigration laws – it was felt that they weren't being naturalised for the 'right' reasons
- In Australia naturalisation of Chinese, and other non-Europeans, was prohibited from 1903 to the mid-1950s, and even earlier in certain of the colonies. In keeping with the ideals of 'White Australia', the government did not want to facilitate the settlement, integration and civic participation of Chinese and other non-Europeans
- For significant parts of the 20th century, then, a period within living memory, Chinese could not be naturalised. But through the family histories I was working on I became interested in the earlier period, the nineteenth century history, when Chinese could be and were naturalised.

7. LINKING LIVES AND LEGISLATION: YEE WING

- In the project I have continued with a research methodology that links legislation and lives.
- I want to understand the law, as it was drafted, debated and enacted, but further than that I want to know how that law was translated into policy, how policy translated into day-to-day administrative practice, and how day-to-day administrative practice affected the lives of ordinary people.

British naturalisation law

- The history of naturalization in the Australasian colonies begins, perhaps unsurprisingly, in the nineteenth century, a time that was, in legal historian Helen Irving's words, 'the hinge between a world where citizenship meant relatively little and a world in which it was profoundly important to the fate of individuals.'¹

¹ Helen Irving, *Citizenship, Alienage, and the Modern Constitutional State: A Gendered History* (Cambridge: University of Cambridge Press, 2016), 49.

- For the colonies, the nineteenth-century was also a time of unprecedented numbers of immigrant ‘settlers’ arriving not only from the United Kingdom, but from Europe, Asia and the United States.
- Until the introduction of the Aliens Act 1844 (UK) (7 & 8 Vic c 66), naturalization of such foreigners in Britain and across the Empire was accomplished by individual Acts of Parliament.²

8. TIMOTHY GOODWIN PITMAN

- The earliest naturalizations in Australasia, for example, were those of two Americans, Timothy Goodwin Pitman, who was actually involved in colonial trade with China, and Prosper de Mestre, who were naturalized by separate Acts of the New South Wales Parliament in 1825.³
- Acts of Parliament granting naturalization to named individuals, either singly or in groups, continued to be enacted in some colonial jurisdictions into the 1860s.
- Here in New Zealand, for example, which was established as a Crown colony separate from New South Wales in 1841, there were twenty such Acts enacted between 1844 and 1866, when the Aliens Act 1866 (NZ) (30 Vict n 17) was introduced.
- The imperial Aliens Act of 1844 introduced a more straightforward, administrative form of naturalization, and this model was followed in corresponding colonial laws.
- New South Wales was the second of the Australasian colonies, following South Australia, to introduce its own Aliens Act (11 Vic n 39). The NSW Act was passed by the colonial parliament in 1847 and granted royal assent two years later in 1849.⁴

² New South Wales and Tasmania (then known as Van Diemen’s Land) did, however, enact legislation regarding denization in 1828 and 1834, respectively. Denization was a separate but related process to naturalization, whereby an alien was granted some of the rights of a British subject, particularly the right to own land. *Denization Act 1828* (NSW) 9 Geo IV n 6, <https://www.legislation.nsw.gov.au/acts/1828-6a.pdf>, and *Denization Act 1834* (Tas) 5 Wil IV n 4,

http://www.austlii.edu.au/au/legis/tas/num_act/aafetltglodicc5win4913.pdf.

³ *Pitman’s Naturalization 1825* (NSW) 6 Geo IV n 13,

<https://www.legislation.nsw.gov.au/acts/1825-12a.pdf>, and *De Mestre’s Naturalization 1825* (NSW) 6 Geo IV n 17, <https://www.legislation.nsw.gov.au/acts/1825-16a.pdf>.

⁴ *Aliens Act 1847* (NSW) 11 Vic n 39, <https://www.legislation.nsw.gov.au/acts/1847-39a.pdf>; *Aliens Act 1846* (SA) No. 7 of 10 Vic,

http://www.austlii.edu.au/au/legis/sa/num_act/aa7o10v1846152.pdf; “Alien Act,” *Sydney Morning Herald*, May 17, 1849, 2, <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article12906941>.

- Under the NSW Aliens Act 1847, to become naturalized an alien had to present a memorial to the Governor – here is an example, the memorial by Ralph Ah How from 1872

9. RALPH AH HOW NATURALISATION MEMORIAL

- The memorial stated their name; age; profession, trade or occupation; duration of residence in the colony; and any other grounds on which he or she sought the rights of a natural-born British subject.
- This memorial was considered by the Governor, who could then grant a certificate of naturalization which was registered with the Supreme Court. The Supreme Court also kept a copy of the certificate. Within sixty days of the grant of the certificate, the memorialist had to swear an oath of allegiance before a judge of the Supreme Court, and pay a fee.
- Both women and men could be naturalized; however, under s 14 a married woman's nationality followed that of her husband, so a foreign woman became a naturalized British subject on her marriage to a natural-born or naturalized British subject.

10. FIRST COLONIAL NATURALISATION LAWS

- Similar legislation, which was primarily aimed at easing the settlement of so-called 'alien friends', was introduced in South Australia in 1846 (20 of 21 Vic); Tasmania (25 Vic n 2) and Queensland in 1861 (25 Vic n 9); Victoria in 1863 (26 Vic n 166), New Zealand in 1866 (30 Vic n 17), and Western Australia in 1871 (35 Vic n 2).
- Over the subsequent decades, colonial naturalization law was refined and localized, in reference to both changes in imperial law and to particular social and economic conditions in each jurisdiction.
- For example, in Victoria, which became a separate Crown colony from New South Wales in 1851, the law relating to aliens was amended three times following its introduction in 1863: in 1865, 1890 and finally in 1896.
- Some of the changes to naturalization law came as colonial boundaries shifted, as territory was claimed or divided or merged, and as the Australasian colonies grew increasingly independent from Britain.
- New South Wales, which was established at Sydney in 1788, expanded to encompass more than half of the Australian continent before gradually assuming its current shape after South Australia, Victoria and Queensland were carved out of its territory,

alongside the establishment of the colonies of Western Australia, Tasmania and New Zealand.

- With the turn of the twentieth century, the five mainland Australian colonies and Tasmania federated to form the Commonwealth of Australia in 1901, while New Zealand, which chose not to become part of the Australian federation, changed from self-governing colony to dominion in 1907.
- Between 1844 and 1923, in the seven colonies and two dominions of Australia and New Zealand, there were more than 50 principal and amendment Acts concerning aliens and naturalization. Imperial laws introduced in 1847 and 1870 (10 & 11 Vic c 83; 33 & 34 Vic c 14) clarified that such colonial legislation could only confer the right of naturalization within the particular colony.
- This territorial limit meant that an Italian naturalized in Victoria would be regarded as a British subject while in Victoria, but as Italian when in Britain or another British colony; outside the British Empire they would, however, be regarded as a British subject, except in their own country of birth.
- As Rieko Karatani has argued, ‘the 1847 and 1870 acts not only confirmed the validity of local naturalization, but they also ended up encouraging colonial governments to strengthen colonial immigration policies of their own’, having provided them with ‘the power to determine who, among the holders of British subjecthood, were entitled to receive citizenship rights and obligations within their territories’.⁵
- The shift from colonies to dominions simplified the legislative context of naturalization, particularly in Australia.

11. FIRST COMMONWEALTH / DOMINION LAW

- There, one new federal law, the *Naturalization Act 1903* (Cth), which came into force from 1904, replaced the six separate colonial laws and recognized the British subject status of those who had earlier taken naturalisation in any of the six colonies.⁶
- The Australasian colonies were immigrant societies, and naturalization was a primary way that colonial governments shaped the make-up of their growing populations.

⁵ Rieko Karatani, *Defining British Citizenship: Empire, Commonwealth and Modern Britain* (Routledge, London and New York: 2014), 56–57.

⁶ On the Naturalization Act 1903 see Kartia Snoek, ‘Empire, Race, Naturalisation: The *Naturalisation Act 1903* (Cth)’, *Melbourne Historical Journal* 40, no. 1 (2012): 103–27.

- As noted, the introduction of naturalization legislation across the colonies was largely done with the aim of turning primarily European immigrants, be they German or Swiss or Swedish, into settlers; naturalization was a way of including these alien immigrants in the colonial project as land and business owners, workers and voters.
- Legislation, regulations and administrative processes were therefore adapted over time as a tool of migrant inclusion and exclusion. In Queensland, for example, which I'm not going to talk about today in any detail, the Aliens Act 1867 set out different requirements for the naturalization of 'Asiatic and African aliens' and 'European and North American aliens', including that Asiatic and African applicants must be married, have lived in the colony for three years, and have their wife living with them at the time of application.
- The Chinese, who were the largest non-white immigrant population in colonial Australia and New Zealand, were the group who primarily encountered the exclusionary power of naturalisation, both by specific laws and regulations as noted above, or through administrative decisions.

Chinese immigration to Australasia

12. LO KEONG FAMILY

- Australia's very first Chinese migrants were men who arrived in the early decades of the nineteenth century on British ships involved in the Canton trade – the first known arrival was in 1803, although it is a man named John Shying, or Mak Sai Ying, who arrived in Sydney two hundred and one years ago in 1818, who is commonly remembered as Australia's first Chinese settler. Starting out as a carpenter, he went on to own a hotel at Parramatta, marry (twice) to European wives, and have a family of sons who later went on to run one of Sydney's best-known firms of undertakers.
- Following scattered arrivals over the following decades, between 1848 and 1852 around 3500 Chinese men were brought to New South Wales as indentured labourers destined for rural properties to work as shepherds and other farm workers. These men were from Fujian province, Hokkien speakers, who left China through the port of Amoy (now Xiamen).
- The first Chinese man known to be in New Zealand was Appo Hocton, who arrived in 1842, who I will speak a bit more about later. And the first Chinese woman was Matilda Lo Keong, who came to Dunedin from Victoria in the mid-1870s, as the wife of fancy goods dealer, Joseph Lo Keong.

13. MAP OF THE PACIFIC

- Gold was, of course, the impetus for large-scale migration of Chinese to the Australasian colonies in the 1850s and 1860s. Beginning with the Californian gold discoveries of the late 1840s, Cantonese men travelled out through Hong Kong across the Pacific to the West Coast of North America, to California and later to British Columbia, from there moving inland to the east.
- As we know, they also went south to Victoria and New South Wales and, from 1861, to Otago at the invitation of the Otago Chamber of Commerce – some of these men had experience in California or had come across from Victoria, while others came directly from Guangdong.
- Although these Cantonese goldseekers are typically thought of as ‘sojourners’, men who came to make a quick fortune and then return to China, there remained what Keir Reeves has called an ‘antipodean epicentre’ of Cantonese who supported subsequent migrations, such as those to Otago and the Palmer River goldfields in Queensland in the 1870s, and these men facilitated Cantonese participation in other economic pursuits such as agricultural work (for example, ringbarking and land-clearing in the Riverina district of New South Wales), market gardening, and work in stores and laundries.

14. CHINESE POPULATION

- If we look quickly at some population figures for Chinese in New South Wales, Victoria, Tasmania and New Zealand, we can see that the Victorian population peaked in the goldrush period, while NSW fluctuated above and below 10,000 across the second half of the nineteenth century. Numbers were very small in Tasmania, and, in fact, make the Chinese population figures for New Zealand look quite impressive.

Chinese restriction and naturalisation

- Just as Cantonese migrants and their communities spread across the British settler colonies of the Pacific Rim, so too did Chinese restriction laws and policies. This history of Chinese restriction is a global story with local inflections, with different laws and policies at different times and in different contexts in each of the colonies.
- Each jurisdiction has a complicated history of debate, enactment, amendment and repeal of their anti-Chinese laws, but as an example let’s look in detail at colonial New South Wales.

- I'm going to be talking about naturalisation and immigration restriction laws here, but it's important to remember that anti-Chinese law and policies did not just relate to immigration, nor were they necessarily explicit in law. Many laws restricted the rights and abilities of 'aliens', so if Chinese were made perpetual aliens through the prohibition of naturalisation, then the 'aliens' laws would also apply to them.

New South Wales

15. OVERVIEW OF CHINESE RESTRICTION LAWS IN NSW

16. 1861 ACT

17. 1881 ACT

18. 1888 ACT

- Colonial NSW was the most explicit in its linking of naturalisation to Chinese restriction, and did so in legislation. The other Australasian colonies, including New Zealand, did it by other means, through administrative practice or by the decision of Cabinet rather than through statute law

19. ALL COLONIES – READ OFF SLIDE

20. NSW CHINESE NATURALISATION OVER TIME

- When we look at naturalisation of Chinese in New South Wales over time we can see very explicitly the link between Chinese restriction and Chinese naturalisation – dips where it is prohibited, of course, but also a sudden jump after the 1881 Act was introduced. Chinese were using naturalisation strategically to facilitate their mobility across colonial borders – it might have been about settlement, but it also about the freedom to move
- 1882–1884: **720** naturalisation certificates were issued to Chinese, about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the total (over 300 in 1883); 1885: **23** certificates issued; 1886: **5** certificates issued 1887: **1** certificate issued. So the NSW government had already begun to restrict Chinese naturalisation, even before it was legislated in 1888.
- Chinese knew and understood the workings of British colonial law, and were strategic in the ways they interacted with it – ultimately this led to tougher and tougher restrictions, but throughout Chinese negotiated their way around the restrictions, they tested the limits of the law through the courts, and they asserted the rights that they did have, including those as British subjects

21. EXEMPTIONS FOR BRITISH SUBJECTS

- If we look at the Chinese restriction laws that were introduced in the 1880s, we can see that there were exemptions of various kinds in place for both naturalised and natural-born British subjects, and I've highlighted them here in blue.

22. CARTOON

- Of all the political cartoons about 'the Chinese Question' published in the colonial newspapers, I've only found a couple that relate to naturalisation, but those I have found highlight this strategic use of naturalisation to avoid punitive Chinese restriction laws. And here, we should remember, that these laws applied to crossing land borders between the colonies, as well as borders by sea.
- Discuss cartoon:
NATURALISED BUT NOT NATURALS
The use of being poll taxed
Our Mongols fail to see;
So they get made into Britishers,
And cut about scot free.

23. CHINESE ARRIVING IN SYDNEY

- You might ask to what extent did naturalised Chinese use these exemptions to travel in and out of the colonies? This slide shows Customs statistics for Chinese arriving into the port of Sydney between 1888 and 1894.
- You can see in the part highlighted in blue that 181 Chinese were permitted to land in Sydney during those six years, and of them 155 had presented naturalisation papers as proof of their right to enter the colony.

New Zealand naturalisation

- So what about New Zealand then?

24. NATURALISATION LEGISLATION IN NEW ZEALAND

- Overview of Chinese naturalisation law in New Zealand – read off slide
- There's a lot more that could be said about New Zealand here, but if you're interested in more details about New Zealand naturalisation and Chinese restriction,

I thoroughly recommend Nigel Murphy's *Guide to Laws and Policies Relating to the Chinese in New Zealand, 1871–1997*.

Naturalised Chinese: who, when, how many?

- As part of my project on Chinese naturalisation I've been putting together databases that record all the Chinese who were naturalised in New Zealand, New South Wales and British Columbia before 1915. I haven't been talking about British Columbia today, but there's also really interesting history there in comparison to Australia and New Zealand.
- There are some published figures of the numbers of naturalised Chinese drawn from government reports and memos, and I'm still tallying up how the figures I'm collating relate to these, but here are some indicative figures for Australia to 1904 when the new federal law came into effect

25. CHINESE NATURALISATION IN AUSTRALIA TO 1904

- Looking at these figures, and remembering the populations statistics I showed you earlier, is anyone game to guess how many Chinese naturalisations I've found in New Zealand to 1907? The answer is 498!

26. APPO HOCTON

- The name of the first Chinese man naturalised in New Zealand is, I'm sure, familiar to you and he's been mentioned already several times at this conference – he was Appo Hocton of Nelson. Hocton had arrived in Nelson in 1842, having worked on English ships first as a cabin boy and then as a steward. In Nelson he initially worked as a housekeeper for a ship's doctor who had arrived on the same boat. Hocton was naturalised in 1852, at the age of 29; he was a cattle breeder who wished to acquire land, which he could not then do as an alien.
- The second Chinese naturalised in New Zealand was a cabinet maker from here in Wellington called John A Tong, who was granted naturalisation 14 years after Hocton, in 1866⁷

⁷ A Tong: http://www.nzlii.org/nz/legis/hist_act/na186630v1866n61308/

27. JOHN A TONG NATURALISATION ACT

- Both Appo Hocton and John A Tong were naturalised before the *Aliens Act 1866* came into force, and so were naturalised through Acts of Parliament⁸
- The first Chinese naturalisation in Australia was in 1854, in Victoria – so New Zealand beat us by two years!

28. FIRST VICTORIA

- In December 1854, three carpenters from Melbourne – Chow Ga Hon (趙宜端), Lain Anding (林亞亭) and Wang Ah Hae (黃亞喜) – became naturalised.

29. FIRST NEW SOUTH WALES

- In New South Wales, the first was a former indentured labourer from Amoy, named Yan Sout, who lived in Grafton – he was naturalised in September 1857.

30. FIRST TASMANIA

- In Tasmania, three Chinese men were the first ones, being granted naturalisation on the same day in June 1882: Quong Kee: Cabinetmaker, Launceston; William A'Ching: Cabinetmaker, Launceston; Yeen Lock: Tin miner, Thomas' Plains

New Zealand

- Among the more familiar names of Chinese naturalised in New Zealand – like Louis Gay Tan and Choie Sew Hoy or Joseph Lo Keong, or perhaps missionaries William Chan or Timothy Fay Loie – there are others that are less well known, and I'm very much enjoying getting to know a new group of people through the archives – NZ naturalisation records are held by Archives New Zealand, here in Wellington.

31. ARCHIVES OF NATURALISATION

- In Australia, naturalisation records are split between the National Archives and the state archives
- Some material in Archives NZ here and in the National Archives of Australia is digitised, and some naturalisation material is also available through ancestry.com

⁸ Hocton: http://www.nzlii.org/nz/legis/hist_act/na185316v1853n4308/

- Naturalisation records offer possibilities for better understanding a community often thought to be transient and marginalised. Certainly, as James Ng has suggested, more Chinese passed through New Zealand than were officially recorded, but what of those who stayed and made a life for themselves? What can the lens of naturalisation tell us about New Zealand's early Chinese communities and the ways they interacted with government authorities and the law?
- Looking in detail, too, at the paperwork associated with naturalisation can reveal details of how exactly Chinese applied for and were granted naturalisation, the length of time the process took, and what complications there might have been along the way. I'm still working through the material on a broad scale, but let's have a look at one case, a pretty straightforward application from 1884, for Jamie Chow Yee of Lawrence.

32. NOTICE IN NEWSPAPER OF JAMIE CHOW YEE'S NATURALISATION

33. JAMIE CHOW YEE MEMORIAL OF NATZ

34. JAMIE CHOW YEE APPLICATION PROCESS

35. TUAPEKA ELECTORAL ROLL

- If we then look at the Tuepeka Electoral Roll for 1896, we can see Jamie Chow Yee's name, along with those of Sam and Amelia Chew Lain, Chow Tie and his wife Grace, and Thomas Chee Chong – these men were all naturalised, and the women's names are there, of course, because of changes brought in 126 years ago with the 1893 Electoral Act, which granted women the vote⁹
- Looking in closely at the records can provide one sort of picture, but looking at the data provided in naturalisation applications as a whole can reveal other things and show patterns over time. I'm still working my way through the data entry from the records for New Zealand as a whole, but let's have a bit of a look:

36. CHINESE NATURALISATIONS IN NEW ZEALAND TO 1907

37. PLACE OF BIRTH

- Top 5 places, and questions around why men who were British subjects by birth would need to become naturalised

⁹ Electoral Act 1893 (57 VICT 1893 No 18)

38, 39, 40. PLACE OF RESIDENCE

- Guess the top 5 places:
- 1. Wellington
- 2. Dunedin
- 3. Auckland
- 4. Palmerston North
- 5. Kumara

41. OCCUPATIONS

- Top 5:
- 1. Storekeeper 2. Gardener
- 3. Miner
- 4. Cook
- 5. Grocer / Market Gardener
- Ship's Steward (Thomas Bowling, Hainan, of Dunedin), Licensed Victualler, Carver and Gilder, Boarding House Keeper, Watchmaker (James Campbell, Shanghai, here in Wellington), Butcher, Draper, Farmer and so on
- Unfortunately, the New Zealand memorials do not explicitly include a reason for naturalisation, other than wanting to settle or remain in the colony, although it is sometimes mentioned in the associated correspondence. Many memorials for New South Wales do state a reason, and from my research to date, I see that the same sorts of reasons apply here

42. REASONS FOR NATURALISATION IN NSW

- Read off slide (remember this is before 1888)

Conclusion

43. HWANG YUNG-LIANG

- In 1909, the Chinese Consul for New Zealand, Hwang Yung-liang (Huáng Róngliáng 黃榮良), stated:

‘Why Chinese wish to become British subjects passed my understanding ... I cannot for the life of me see where they are to benefit by becoming British subjects while they are held in contempt by the people who grant them the privilege. I see no objection whatever to their becoming naturalised British subjects providing that they are placed on an equality with other British subjects. Otherwise the arrangement is one-sided.’¹⁰

- Huang’s comments came after New Zealand, and Australia, had stopped naturalising Chinese

44. END OF CHINESE NATURALISATION

- Read off slide
- And it would be another four decades until Chinese in New Zealand and Australia would once again be able to be naturalised.

45. TUTOY CHINN, CHARLES WONG HEE

- It’s important to remember, though, that those children born in Australia and New Zealand to Chinese parents continued to gain British nationality at birth, and those Chinese who had been naturalised in the colonies retained their British subject status.
- So, it was in the 1950s that Chinese naturalisation began again in New Zealand and Australia.
- **In New Zealand 1951** – Cabinet approved the resumption of naturalisation of Chinese on four conditions: their primary loyalty was to NZ, they complied with the normal requirements for naturalisation, they formally renounced their Chinese citizenship, and that they demonstrated they were closer to the NZ way of life than the Chinese
- **New Zealand 1958** – The requirement that they renounce their Chinese citizenship was removed and they were able to obtain naturalisation on the same conditions as others

¹⁰ CHINAMEN ABROAD, *Southland Times*, 8 April 1909, <https://paperspast.natlib.govt.nz/newspapers/ST19090408.2.43>. Image: <https://paperspast.natlib.govt.nz/newspapers/NZTR19110318.2.27.1>

- **Australia 1956** – Cabinet extended the right of naturalisation to non-Europeans admitted before Federation and those who had been admitted since Federation but had been permitted to remain without restriction
- **Australia 1957** – Naturalisation further extended to allow non-Europeans of good character who had resided in Australia for at least 15 years to become Australian citizens
- During that time though Chinese didn't stop applying for naturalisation, and they didn't stop testing their rights as naturalised or natural-born British subjects.
- In 1923, for example, 89-year-old John Booshang of Adaminaby, in the Snowy Mountains in New South Wales, applied to be naturalised. He had been in Australia since 1852 – living in Sydney, Melbourne, Ballarat, Kiandra and Cooma before making his home of 50 years in Adaminaby. He had a white Australian wife and eight Australian-born children, and had never returned to China. His reason for requesting naturalisation at this time? So, his wife, Anastasia, could receive the Old Age Pension – one of their sons had come home from the Great War an invalid who needed his mother's care.
- In the context of 'White New Zealand' and 'White Australia', Consul Hwang perhaps had a point – what good was British nationality if you didn't have the same rights as other British subjects?
- From what we know about Chinese naturalised in New Zealand and Australia in the nineteenth century, I think perhaps what British subjecthood did was give Chinese settlers with another weapon to fight, or at least negotiate their way around, racially discriminatory anti-Chinese laws and policies
- Naturalisation was one way that Chinese used the power of the law to test the racialised limits of belonging in their adopted homelands.